

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COGNITIVE ACTIVITY.

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Abstract: This article describes the theoretical foundations of the development of cognitive activity of students. The article presents as information the theoretical opinions of teachers and psychologists regarding the development of a student's cognitive activity.

Key words: cognitive activity, development of students' cognitive activity, educational activity.

In our republic and in foreign countries, the psychological foundations of the development of cognitive activity of students are studied, experiences of the development of cognitive activity are studied from a theoretical and practical point of view. Cognitive psychology (Latin *cognitio* "knowledge") is a psychology focused on the mathematical modeling of experience and thinking. Department of Psychology, studying memory, attention, emotions. Many principles of cognitive psychology underlie modern psycholinguistics. The results of cognitive psychology are widely used in other areas of psychology, in particular, in social psychology, personality psychology, educational psychology, and also in the construction of artificial intelligence systems.

The problem of the development of cognitive activity is one of the most pressing problems in psychology. Cognitive activity as a psychological phenomenon is a two-way interconnected process: on the one hand, cognitive activity is a form of self-organization and self-awareness of the student; on the other hand, cognitive activity is considered as the result of special actions of the teacher in organizing the student's cognitive activity.

Therefore, when defining cognitive activity, we need to have an idea of what type or aspect of cognitive activity we are talking about. At the same time, we should not forget that the end result of the teacher's efforts is the transformation of the student's specially organized activity into independent activity, a process of self-education. Thus, both types of cognitive activity are closely related to each other.

In psychology, the definition of the concept "Cognitive activity" primarily characterizes the student's position in cognitive activity. In a number of studies, the problem of studying cognitive activity was considered in the context of creativity.

Kharlamov interpreted cognitive activity as “an active state of a student, characterized by his desire to learn, mental effort and the manifestation of voluntary actions in the process of acquiring knowledge.” In enhancing the cognitive activity of students, an important role is played by the teacher’s ability to encourage students to understand the logic and consistency in the presentation of educational material, and to highlight the basic and important rules in it. At primary school age, it is useful to teach children to independently identify the most important thing in the teacher’s explanations and formulate the most important questions presented in the lesson.

In order to actively perceive and understand the material being studied, it is of great importance for the teacher to be able to give his presentation a charming character, make it lively and interesting. First of all, we should not forget that the educational material itself contains many stimuli that stimulate the interest and mental activity of students. These include the novelty of scientific information, the clarity of facts, the uniqueness of conclusions, a unique approach to considering established ideas, and deep insight into the essence of events.

G.I. Shchukina believes that the source of cognitive activity is cognitive interest. In his opinion, interest is a person’s active emotional and cognitive attitude towards something. Cognitive curiosity activates all human mental processes; at a high level of its development, it motivates a person to constantly seek to change reality through activity. Characteristics of cognitive activity are independence in activity, the research nature of activity, initiative in choosing the content and methods of activity, active acceptance of conditions that encourage engaging in cognitive activity. Curiosity, inquisitiveness, readiness for cognitive activity, “thirst for knowledge” - all these are various manifestations of a person’s cognitive orientation, based on cognitive interest, which determines an active attitude towards the world and the process of knowing it.

D.M.Vinogradov and I.B. Pervin believed that collective cognitive activity plays an important role in the development of cognitive activity. Its various forms stimulate creativity, fantasy, imagination, cognitive activity and independence. Students should be taught to work as a team. Every student should have the opportunity to acquire business communication skills and be able to provide and receive assistance. It is equally important to create an atmosphere of mutual respect, goodwill, attention to each other and sensitivity in the classroom so that each student has a positive attitude towards learning and actively participates in it

In the development of cognitive activity, Kabanova considers the system of forming generalized methods of educational work, which, according to Kabanova, are important components of effective educational activity of students. Methods of cognitive activity are methods of mental work that ensure the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities, their independent application and active change. Using a system of means to activate students' cognitive activity until they understand the purpose of the activity at the stage of forming a cognitive motive. creative use contributes to the formation of productive independent work skills and generalized learning skills.

Z.I. Kalmykova believed that the leading condition for the development of cognitive activity is problem-based learning. The problem principle is aimed at discovering new knowledge and is the leading principle of developmental learning. Problem-based learning is learning in which the initial stage of acquiring knowledge and developing intellectual skills occurs in a relative process - a system of independent problem solving - problems that arise under the general guidance of a teacher. Only those tasks are problematic, and their solution is directed by the teacher, but involves an independent search for patterns, methods of action and rules that are still unknown to the student. Such tasks stimulate active mental activity, supported by interest, and the "discovery" made by the students themselves brings them emotional satisfaction.

I. S. Yakimanskaya made a great contribution to cognitive activity. According to him, not all training really has a developmental effect, although it does not exclude the cognitive activity of students. Cognitive activity is the most important source of mental development only when it becomes an independent activity. The formation of this initiative is the most important task of developmental education. IS. As Yakimanskaya noted, "mental activity" is determined by the personal, one-sided "attitude of the student to the acquired knowledge," such an attitude characterizes a subjective position. A student is not only an object of learning, but also a subject. He not only assimilates the teacher's requirements, but also assimilates them, selectively reacts to them, actively assimilates and processes them, taking into account his personal experience and level of intellectual development. At the same time, he used the term "mental" and not "cognitive", but considered them synonymous.

In our opinion, these concepts should be distinguished from each other, since the term "mental activity" describes a certain level of mastery of several mental operations and is the result of cognitive activity. As for "cognitive activity," it is incomplete and includes the process of acquiring knowledge.

“Activity in educational activities is not only the state of the student’s activity, but also the quality of this activity, in which the student’s personality is manifested in relation to the content, nature and activity of his activity. the desire to mobilize one’s spiritual and volitional efforts to achieve educational and cognitive goals.

This definition seems to be the most complete, since it reflects not only the psychological aspects of cognitive activity (the state of activity, the quality of this activity), but also its social aspects (the personality of the student and his attitude to the content and content). nature of activity), and also names the means that activate cognitive activity: interest, development of the motivational field, volitional qualities (a person’s desire to mobilize spiritual and volitional efforts) and the specific purpose of using these actions (achieving an educational and cognitive goal).

As a result of the development of cognitive activity and the use of forms of effective organization of educational activities, advanced knowledge and skills are created. As a result, potential young people in our country are growing up as specialists

Used Books:

1. <https://goaravetisyan.ru/uz/teoreticheskie-osnovy-razvitiya-poznavatelnoi-aktivnosti-problema/>
2. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "Development of cognitive activity in future teachers." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.4 (2021): 705-708.
3. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "THE SIGNIFICANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL CONDITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS." *E Conference Zone*. 2023.
4. Yuldasheva, M., M. Nurmatova, and O. Tolipova. "ADVANTAGES OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION."
5. Yuldasheva, Malohat, and Feruza Rakhimova. "THE INTRODUCTION OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES." *Ученый XXI века* 6-2 (2016): 72-74.
6. Erkinovna, Yuldasheva Malohat. "THE MECHANISM OF USING EDUCATIONAL PROJECTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH." *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal* 11.3 (2023): 127-129.

7. Olimovich. (2023). MAKTABGA TAYYORLASHNING ILMIIY PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 876–881. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.748>
8. Parpiyev Odiljon Olimovich. (2023). RIVOJLANISH VOSITASI SIFATIDA TRIZ TEXNOLOGIYASINING XUSUSIYATLARI . ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 24(1), 17–20. Retrieved from <https://www.newjournal.org/index.php/01/article/view/7877>
9. Parpiyev, O., & Pozilov, H. (2023, June). BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA TOPISHMOQLARNING AHAMIYATI. In Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования (Vol. 5, No. 2, pp. 63-74).
10. Mannonova Muxarramabonu, & Odiljon Parpiyev. (2023). AUDIOLINGVAL METODNING AFZALLIKLARI. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 882–887. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.749>
11. Muazzamxon Xodjayeva, & Odiljon Parpiyev. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLAR O'QUVCHILARINING O'QISH VA SAVODXONLIK DARAJASINI OSHIRISHDA XALQARO BAHOLASH DASTURLARINING AHAMIYATI. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 914–918. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.758>
12. Ochildiyeva Mushtariy, & Parpiyev Odiljon. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIM TIZIMIGA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLAR. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 640–644. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.666>
13. Xushbaqova Zarnigor Javliyevna, & Odiljon Parpiyev. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA NUTQIY SAVODXONLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 645–650. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.667>
14. Mannonova Muxarramabonu, & Odiljon Parpiyev. (2023). AUDIOLINGVAL METODNING AFZALLIKLARI. QO'QON UNIVERSITETI XABARNOMASI, 1(1), 882–887. <https://doi.org/10.54613/ku.v1i1.749>

